

ROWING WITH THE HELP OF SPECIAL EQUIPMENT AND METHODS OF BALANCE DEVELOPMENT IN CANOEING

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Abstract

Based on the data, we developed a balance development system in which motor movements (walking, jumping, twisting and turning) are associated with maintaining balance. It actively ensures the normal functioning of all physiological systems of the body, stimulates the manifestation of the optimal range of movements, determines the rational distribution of muscle power, as a result, more rational use of energy in maintaining balance and effective motor activity [8].

Key words: the ability to coordinate movement, body balance in space and time, effective distribution of muscle power, balance in motor activity, rowing and canoeing, analyzers.

A certain body balance is required to perform the movements of rowing and canoeing. It is impossible to achieve a certain level of mastering the effective technique of motor movement without the appropriate level of development of keeping the position of the body in the balance space [1, 10, 12, 13, 16].

Balance is one of the main types of movement coordination that rowers must learn and train in training [7, 8, 12, 15].

The purpose of the study was to theoretically confirm the balance system in

rowing and canoeing.

Training devices are part of the system of developing the ability to maintain balance; These devices contribute to the dynamic development of all physiological systems of the body, develop the amplitude, speed and rhythm of rowing movements, optimize the effective location of body parts , and thus ensure balance. Carrying out specific preparatory exercises aimed at improving balance significantly increases the body's ability to balance in space and directly affects balance during canoeing. Rowing and canoeing, especially the latter, require the ability of the body to maintain balance in the boat, so it is necessary to develop **a certain (water) balance** (*This balance is associated with water sports, which involve the body in a boat with complex movements requires an effective ability to balance*) .

Designed training devices help to develop the rower's ability to maintain balance, which ensures a successful transition from the device to a real boat on the water. The developed system of special physical exercises on the devices helps to improve the balance more quickly and qualitatively and helps to master rowing technique effectively. Exercises improve spatial and temporal orientation and develop body balance in different positions (on two legs, on one leg, then on the other, and in a canoe). Inadequate body balance is a major obstacle to mastering effective rowing techniques; training tools are used to develop and improve this special (water) balance ability. Therefore, body balance is one of the main skills of movement coordination, which should be constantly improved.

Body balance is a certain position of the body in space and time, which opposes the force of gravity of the Earth. A better rower overcomes and uses the force of gravity; the more effectively he maintains body balance, the more rowing devices help him . [1,11,21,25]

One way to balance the body is to overcome gravity by moving the body's center of gravity closer to the boat's seat. Various exercises to develop balance

help to effectively place all parts of the body in space. For example, squatting on a wooden floor with a diameter of 300-400 mm is more effective for maintaining balance than simply walking. Effective positioning of body parts in static and dynamic movements is one of the most important components of balance.

In the "Explanatory dictionary of sports terms" body balance is described as a state of *stable position of the body in static and dynamic situations* [2,3,4,12,16].

According to LD Nazarenko, body balance *is the ability to maintain a stable position of the body and its parts in supported and unsupported stages of motor movement* [13,14].

V. M. Zatsiorsky defines balance as *the ability to maintain a stable body position in various movements and poses* [7,9,15,16,21,23].

Carrying out various physical exercises aimed at improving balance ensures the emergence of effective methods of rowing movements, which, according to NA Bernstein [2, 3,4,5,13,17,19], helps to efficiently conserve energy. will help. Not all the energy used for rowing is useful, as some of that energy is used to overcome resistance forces. Inadequate movement coordination impairs rowing technique and increases energy expenditure. Maintaining body balance is related *to minimizing the number of degrees of freedom* , which increases body balance [14]. **Stable equilibrium** is the ability of a mechanical system to regain its initial state after a small disturbance.

balance development system includes motor activity that implements hundreds of degrees of freedom in different directions; however, effective performance is primarily characterized by *low degrees of freedom* and proper rowing technique. A number of degrees of freedom (more than 20) are activated during rowing exercises on the training machine, which makes it difficult to control the movement. Movements performed with the help of a rowing machine allow you to significantly reduce the number of movement errors and prevent the

constant retraining that is inevitable in comfortable rowing exercises. A decrease in the degree of freedom in special exercises leads to muscle retention. Therefore, it is possible to maintain balance while exercising in a rowing boat. [1,11,21,25]

Rowing sports, especially kayaking and canoeing, are characterized by static and dynamic balance. In such training, the rower's body is not stable, it constantly vibrates. The rower "loses" his balance for a moment and then regains it. *In this case, it seems that the balance is not lost, but rather quickly found.*

Based on the theory and technique of physical education and sports training, as well as our many years of pedagogical experience, we **can conclude on the need to introduce a definition of static stability of balance: it is the rower 's ability to coordinate maintaining balance. Despite the harsh biomechanical conditions, the static position of the athlete is a stable vertical body position for a long time, in which weak movements of the front leg and pulling back of the pelvis are balanced by performing complex rowing movements.**

The balance development system mainly consists of exercises aimed at developing cosmic body balance. During these exercises, the muscles are very tense and they use maximum effort to maintain balance. Boats designed for the development of balance help to master the technique of rowing and ensure intra-muscular and inter-muscular coordination with the preservation of body parts. For example, an athlete needs high activity of the muscles of the back, arms and legs; constant use *and redistribution* of muscle movements aimed at maintaining balance occurs.

The designed system of balance improvement ensures the maintenance of body balance, which determines the degree of orientation in space. The higher this level, the easier it is to balance. Space orientation during rowing in machines, *the movement of the body and its parts in the conditions of rowing simulation* determines

Accuracy of movement is of great importance when performing special

exercises aimed at maintaining balance . For example, the technique of rowing includes a structured and specific movement cycle, and information about its parameters is given to the control unit through certain channels.

The concepts of "sense of balance", "sense of water ", "sense of boat" are the basis of rowing technique. These concepts are closely related to the set of functional systems that allow you to control rowing movements and body balance during training. In rowing boats, it is recommended to perform some elements of the exercises with the eyes closed, which will be more difficult than with the eyes open.

Thus, a special physical exercise system designed to develop balance with the help of training simulators has been proven to be effective in developing the correct level of balance through effective placement of body parts, minimizing the degree of freedom of the motor system, timely distribution and redistribution. Muscle movements with a high level of spatial orientation, which is impossible without appropriate physical and special training.

The role of analyzers in controlling the balance is high. The motor analyzer is important in performing motor movements to maintain balance. But visual, vestibular, tactile, autonomic and kinesthetic analyzers are also actively connected with a particular sport.

Conclusion. Balance exercises on land, along with special conditioning exercises performed in training boats, increase the rower's muscle strength. In rowing, beginners try to maintain balance more than trained athletes.

REFERENCES.

1. Sherali Khoshimovich Gafurov , Bahadir Khoshimovich Gafurov 5X5 FOOTBALL IN UZBEKISTAN SPORTS TYPE PUBLICATION THROUGH SEE IN THE CAPACITY DEFECT There is PERSONS ACTION ACTIVITY DEVELOPMENT // Scientific progress. 2022. #6. URL : <https://cyberleninka> .

ru / article / n / popularization of the 5 x 5 football sport in Uzbekistan , or the development of the activity of people with the ability to reach it (data obrascheniya : 15.11.2022 _ _ _ _ _)

2. Sherali Khoshimovich G. Ofurov , Bakhodir _ Khoshimovich G. Ofurov _ PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES FROM A CARRIAGE USED SPINE GRANDMOTHER _ _ DAMAGED YOUNG PEOPLE ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION // Scientific progress . 2022. #6. URL : <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptive-physical-education-of-disabled-wheelchair-injured-young-people-spine-pog-mother> (data obrascheniya : 15.11.2022).

3. Sherali Hoshimovich Gofurov METHODS OF DEVELOPING SPORTS TRAINING OF SKILLED SPRINTERS // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. #4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/methods-of-developing-sports-training-of-skilled-sprinters> (data obrashcheniya: 13.12.2022).

4. Eofurov Sh. Formation of self-development abilities of athletes through means of physical education. - 2020.

5 . Sherali Hoshimovich Ghofurov, Dilshod Bakhtiyor Ogli Bakhtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov ORGANIZING THE TRAINING OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH ATHLETICS EXERCISES // Scientific progress. 2022. #1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-school-age-school-age-children-through-athletic-athletics-meshqlari-workouts> (data obrashcheniya: 13.12.2022).

6 . Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Methods of training development of short-distance runners //Scientific progress. – 2021. – no. 8.

7 . PHYSICAL L. , THEORETICAL T ., DEVELOPMENT S. _ Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. No. Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/physical-theoretical-development> (data) transaction : 12.01. 2022).

8 . TRAINING GROUP FOR THE TRAINING OF ATHLETES IN SPORTS SCHOOLS FOR CHILDREN AND YOUNG PEOPLE GofurovSh //X. To Fan-Sport. - 2020. - No. 5. - S. 38-40.

9 . Eofurov Sh . ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE WITH SPINE INJURIES USING A WHEELCHAIR // MEJDUNARODNAYA NAUCHNO - PRACTICAL ONLINE CONFERENCE . - 2021. - T. 4. - S. 24.

10. EOFUROV Sh. IMPROVING THE TASKS OF ATHLETES PLAYING IN THE PRIMARY PREPARATORY GROUP IN THEIR SCHOOLS. - 2020.

11 . Sherali Hoshimovich GO METHODS OF DEVELOPING SPORTS TRAINING OF QUALIFIED SPRINTERS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – no. 4.

1 2 . Gofurov SX et al. A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES // ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. - 2022. - T. 11. – no. 12. - S. 179-189.

13 . Sherali Hoshimovich GO et al. Scientific progress. 2022. No. 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-training-for-preschool-age-children-through-athletics-exercises> (data obrascheniya: 04.02. 2022).

14. Sherali Hoshimovich G'furov, Dilshod Bakhtiyor Oghli Bakhtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov ORGANIZING TRAINING OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH ATHLETICS EXERCISES // Scientific progress. 2022. #1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-school-age-children-athletic-athletic-training-through-exercises> (data obrashcheniya: 16.12.2022).

15. Sherali Hoshimovich G'furov, Dilshod Bakhtiyor Oghli Bakhtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov ORGANIZING THE TRAINING OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH ATHLETICS EXERCISES // Scientific

progress. 2022. #1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-school-age-school-age-children-with-athletic-athletic-meshqlari-workouts> (data obrashcheniya: 16.12.2022).

16. Sherali Hoshimovich GO, Dilshod Bakhtiyor OG, Lee Bakhtiyorov UAS Organizing training of preschool children through athletics exercises //Scientific progress. – 2022. – no. 1.

17 . Dilshod Bakhtiyorovich Bakhtiyorov TOOLS AND METHODS OF PHYSICAL TRAINING OF AMPUTANT FOOTBALL PLAYERS // Scientific progress. 2022. #2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-physical-tarbiya-vositalari-va-usyugyi> (data obrashcheniya: 16.12.2022).

18 . Hoshimovich GS, Duszhanov BM, Abdumavlanovich TU IMPROVEMENT OF THE TRAINING PROCESS OF FLIGHT AND ATHLETES IN THE INITIAL TRAINING GROUP OF YOUTH //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. - 2022. - T. 11. – no. 12. - S. 163-176.

19. GOFUROV Sh. X. IMPROVING TRAINING OF ATHLETES ENGAGED IN PRIMARY PREPARING GROUPS IN SPORTS SCHOOLS FOR CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS //Fan-Cportga. - 2020. - No. 5. - S. 38-40.

20. Sherali Khoshimovich Gofurov, Bakhodir Khoshimovich Gofurov ADAPTIVE PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE WITH SPINE INJURIES USING A WHEELCHAIR // Scientific progress. 2022. #6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptive-physical-training-of-injured-youth-using-a-wheelchair-using-a-spinal-pog-mother> (data obrashcheniya: 09.01.2023).

21. Gofurov, SX, Berdiyeva, CA, Berdiyev, SD, & Atabayev, AN (2022). A STRATIFIED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF GIRLS WITH DISABILITIES. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF*

MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603 , 11 (12), 179-189.

22. Hoshimovich, GS, Hoshimovich, GB, & Ibrahim Oglu, KS (2022). Differentiated Approach to Improving the Physical Qualities of Students With Disabilities. *Eurasian Research Bulletin* , 15 , 213-223.

23. Sherali Hoshimovich Gofurov METHODS OF DEVELOPING TRAINING OF SHORT DISTANCE RUNNERS // Scientific progress. 2021. #8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/methods-of-training-development-of-short-distance-running-athletes> (data obrascheniya: 09.01.2023).

24. Sherali Hashimovich G. Ofurov , Dilshad _ Happily O'G'Lee _ _ _ _ _ Bakhtiyarov , Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov PRIOR TO SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN LIGHTWEIGHT ATHLETICS EXERCISES THROUGH EXERCISE TOOLS _ ORGANIZATION ACHIEVEMENT // Scientific progress . 2022. #1. URL : [https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-pre-school-children's-training-through-athletics-exercises](https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/organization-of-pre-school-children-s-training-through-athletics-exercises) (data obrascheniya : 15.11.2022) _ _ _ _ _

25. Erkin Nazarovich Sirliiev, Aziz Hashimjon Oguli Uzokov PSYCHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING PRIORITY QUALITIES IN THE PERSONALITY OF DZYUDOCH // CARJIS. 2021. #3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/psychological-a-amiyati-of-studying-the-priority-characteristic-of-personality> (data obrashcheniya: 09.01.2023).